

INOUETS OF WASTEWATER TREATMENT IN TASHKENT AND PROSPECTS FOR THEIR FURTHER DEVELOPMENT

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Introduction. The total area of the city of Tashkent is 438.49 m², the number of permanent residents taken into account is 2,909,500 [1]. According to experts, it is estimated that there will be a population of more than 4 million people when considering the capital for a certain period and with guests arriving daily. These consumers form the basis of municipal effluents that form in the capital.

In addition, about 30,000 enterprises and organizations drain the wastewater generated in them into the municipal wastewater networks.

Today, an average of 1.7 million m³ of wastewater from the population and enterprises and organizations in this capital and adjacent areas is being treated and restored by the Tashkent City Water Supply JSC [2].

Annotation:. In the article, proposals were developed on the example of the wastewater treatment system of Tashkent and the city of Tashkent on the issues of the sewage treatment system of the Republic, their analysis and further improvement of the current state.

The effluent generated from 12 districts and adjacent areas in Tashkent City is being treated by the "Buzsuv" saturation facility, "Salar" saturation facility, and "Bektemir" wastewater treatment facilities. Wastewater treatment in all of these facilities is carried out in a classical way, that is, it is mainly intended to purify the wastewater generated from the utility farm. Wastewater treatment is carried out through mechanical and biological treatment and detoxification steps. Wastewater treatment involves very complex technological processes.

Today, the level of provision of the capital's population with wastewater service today is 93.4% [4].

The "Buzsuv" saturation facility was commissioned in 1963. It mainly receives the effluents of Yunusabad, Almazar, Shaykhontohur, Chilonzor, Uchtepa and partly Zangiota districts, and receives an average of 680,000 m³ of effluents per day, returning the treated effluents to the Bozsuv canal below [2].

Draw 1. Drawing of the saturation facility "Buzsuv" in the cross section of the areas receiving wastewater

The wastewater being treated at the facility is neutralized by hypochlorite-sodium produced by electrolysis at the final stage. The facility has its own "Ximbaklaboratory", conducting chemical and Bacteriological Analysis.

The "Salar" saturation facility was commissioned in 1961. It mainly receives the effluents of Sergeli, Yangihayat, Mirabad, Yashnabod, Yakkasaroy and Mirzo Ulugbek districts and receives an average of 840,000 m³ of effluents per day, returning the treated effluents to the Salar canal below [2].

Draw 2. Drawing of the "Salar" saturation facility in the cross section of areas receiving wastewater

The wastewater being treated at the facility is neutralized by hypochlorite-sodium produced by electrolysis at the final stage. The facility has its own "Ximbaklaboratory", conducting chemical and Bacteriological Analysis.

As a result of the construction of apartment buildings and the development of industrial enterprises in the city of Tashkent, the load on the

wastewater service is increasing. While the volume of wastewater coming to the pumping station "KNS-3", which drives effluent in Sergeli district, has led to an increase in the volume of effluent to an average of 170 thousand m³ per day, with the creation of the new state district, the need for a wastewater network is causing further increase [3].

The "Bektemir" wastewater treatment facility was commissioned in 1976, designed primarily to purify the wastewater from consumers in Bektemir district. An average of 21,000 m³ of effluent per day is received and treated through the facility and dumped into the Chirchiq River. In the process of cleaning in the facility, mechanical and biological methods are used. Disinfection work is carried out using a hypochlorite-sodium chemical agent. The facility has its own "Ximbaklaboratory" with chemical and bacteriological analytical control [2].

Secondary contamination with nitrates and nitrites is observed in the saturation facilities "Buzsuv" and "Salar" but does not exceed the permissible concentration throw.

In 2022, 37 norms connected to the wastewater network of Tashkent Water Supply LLC were identified by legal entities and individual entrepreneurs draining the wastewater of over-contaminated production, and measures for the effective use of the first local sewage treatment facilities owned by these entities are not being taken. [3]

Sewage effluents of non-standard concentration into the centralized wastewater network are mainly textile, skin processing, paper processing, meat and dairy processing enterprises, as well as poultry houses.

The dumping of sewage from these enterprises through local wastewater facilities into centralized wastewater networks that have not undergone preliminary treatment processes, in excess of the permissible norm, reduces the cleaning efficiency of sewage treatment facilities, leading to the spread of bad smell along its trajectory of sewage.

In 2022, 20 enterprises (*skin processing, textile, poultry and paper processing*) that dumped sewage in a centralized wastewater network in a concentration exceeding the permissible norm were disconnected from the network [3].

It should be noted that the increase in industrial and other facilities from 12 districts of the city of Tashkent is increasing from the project capacity of wastewater networks. The effluent produced is mainly from "Salar" as well as "Buzsuv" effluent treatment facilities. The structures are not able to completely clean water contaminated with chemicals and heavy metal ions.

The increase in the population and industrial enterprises in the city of Tashkent and adjacent regions can lead to an increase in the load on the existing wastewater system in the future and, as a result, to a failure of the system.

On the second hand, the sewage treatment facilities "Salar" and "Bektemir", which remain within the city, are operating at full capacity, causing discontent among the surrounding population over the release of an unpleasant

smell at certain times.

Therefore, to solve the problems that have arisen, to increase the capacity of "Salar" and "Buzsuv" wastewater treatment plants by 100,000 m³/day each, to increase the capacity of the "Salar" wastewater treatment plant by 1060,000 m³/day, as part of the project "modernization of drinking and wastewater networks in Tashkent" of the European bank for reconstruction and development in 2023 - 2024, it is planned to be brought from the day to 830 thousand m³/day [2].

It is planned to build a new wastewater treatment plant with a capacity of 1.5 million m³/day, mainly in the territory of Tashkent region, Quyichirchik District, "Surum" LLC, which will be assigned at the government level to address the expansion of the city of Tashkent, increasing number of consumers and existing problems.

With the launch of this project, there will be an opportunity to stop the activities of the pumping station "KNS-3" and wastewater treatment facilities "Bektemir" in the Sergeli district, as well as to lighten part of the load falling on the "Salar" saturation facility.

In addition, it is expected to increase the quality of services to the population in the newly annexed regions and districts of Sergeli and Yangiheyat.

The activities of industrial enterprises to dispose of wastewater generated from production into the sewer network of utilities of the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan of February 3, 2010

Approved by Resolution 11, it is established that the regulation is based on the "rules for the adoption of production wastewater and the procedure for calculating the compensation fees for non-regulatory discharge of pollutants into the municipal wastewater networks of cities and other settlements of the Republic of Uzbekistan".

But as a result of the insufficient economic mechanism in this decision, the requirements for the local wastewater treatment plant, the primary treatment of wastewater in industrial enterprises, remain unfulfilled.

Based on the requirements of the resolution, the low cost of compensation payments paid by production enterprises in exchange for the disposal of contaminated sewage into the municipal sewer network without primary treatment facilities, the construction and disposal of local treatment facilities by industrial enterprises are pushed back.

There are also no national standards in the direction of wastewater quality control.

Conclusion. The composition of wastewater coming from industrial enterprises (*mainly aviaries, poultry, leather and flax processing cexes, textile enterprises*) to wastewater treatment facilities does not meet the norm level requirement, which in turn leads to the failure of the technological cleaning process of wastewater treatment facilities and the destruction of microorganisms contained in the active well in the biological treatment process.

In addition, it is necessary to constantly continue the work of maintaining

existing systems without constant handling, to ensure the effectiveness of projects carried out at the expense of funds from international molilya institutions.

In accordance with the aim of the industrial enterprises to revise the compensation fees and develop national standards in the direction of wastewater quality control for the production of wastewater generated by utilities to the wastewater network in excess of the normative discharge.

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